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ABSTRACT

Re-emerging viral infections pose a significant public health threat in Europe due to factors such as climate change, migration, urbanization, antimicrobial resistance, and disruptions in vaccination programs. A large proportion of these pathogens are zoonotic, necessitating an ecological perspective in risk assessment. The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated risks by reducing vaccination coverage, leading to the resurgence of diseases such as measles, poliomyelitis, and pertussis. Climate-driven vector expansion has also increased arboviral infections, including West Nile virus and Dengue. Meanwhile, MPox and Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever highlight the persistent threat of zoonotic spillover. A One Health approach, integrating human, animal, and environmental health strategies, is critical for epidemic preparedness. Strengthening surveillance, vaccination programs, and interdisciplinary collaboration is essential to mitigate these threats. Future efforts should focus on predictive zoonotic models, climate-resilient health systems, and equitable vaccine distribution to enhance global health security.

KEYWORDS

Arboviruses, one health, re-emerging infectious diseases, vaccination hesitancy, zoonoses

INTRODUCTION

Factors such as climate change, natural disasters, wars, increased migration, globalization, urbanization, antimicrobial resistance, anti-vaccination movement and increased global connectivity, and increased interactions between wildlife and humans make emerging and re-emerging viral infections in Europe a serious threat to public health (Elias, Nkengasong, & Qadri, 2021; Semenza & Paz, 2021; Wang et al., 2024). These changes are both changing the epidemiology of viral infections in Europe by introducing previously unrecognized viral strains in the region, and facilitating the transmission of these viruses, thus increasing the risk of epidemics. Large proportion of emerging/re-emerging pathogens are zoonoses. Risk assessments need an ecological perspective to understand the dynamics of these pathogens in light of climate change and changes in agricultural practices (Medlock & Jameson, 2010).

The disruptions experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in routine vaccination programs, have led to decreased coverage of many vaccines (Minta et al., 2023). In addition, mass migration movements are also considered an important risk factor for the re-emergence of infectious diseases. For example, the entry of approximately 3.5 million refugees into Türkiye after the Syrian civil war concretizes this risk (Ergönül et al., 2020).

Under these conditions, vaccine-preventable diseases such as measles, whooping cough, diphtheria, and poliovirus have once again become a threat (Medlock & Jameson, 2010). The geographical spread of tropical diseases, along with increased international travel and vector spread (Jiménez-Morillas et al., 2019), has made the role of primary care physicians even more critical in recognizing infections with high contagiousness and lethality. Family physicians need to take an active role in disease prevention by considering variables such as vaccination rates, the status of the immigrant population, and gaps in herd immunity.

Emerging and re-emerging viral infections are increasingly common and pose serious public health threats due to their ability to affect the immune system. These pathogens can trigger excessive immune responses, causing severe immunopathological conditions that can lead to tissue damage, systemic inflammation, multiple organ failure, and death. Although inflammation is a fundamental component of the immune

response, uncontrolled responses, especially to newly encountered viruses, can lead to fatal outcomes (Gogoi, Baruah, & Narain, 2024).

Below are mentioned important viral threats that are increasing in Europe and our country due to the reasons listed above.

SOME KEY VIRAL THREATS ON THE RISE IN EUROPE

Mpox

MPox, the most critical Orthopoxvirus infection to emerge after the eradication of smallpox and the cessation of vaccination, poses a significant global zoonotic threat. Its spread beyond the African continent and its change in zoonotic transmission dynamics have raised concerns among international health organizations, including the World Health Organization (WHO) (Nageeb, Ghonaim, & Li, 2025). In 2022–2023, significant MPox outbreaks occurred in non-endemic areas of Europe for the first time. Although the rapid availability of vaccines in Europe has effectively reduced cases, there are still gaps in the surveillance systems (Ianache et al., 2024).

Arboviruses (West Nile Virus, Dengue, Zikavirus, Chikungunya)

Arboviruses are viruses transmitted by arthropods such as mosquitoes, ticks, and sandflies. They can cause common symptoms such as fever, headache, myalgia, and fatal neurological complications (Srichawla et al., 2024). Climate change has increased mosquito populations, leading to increased cases of West Nile virus and Dengue in southern Europe (Matlack et al., 2024).

West Nile Virus: West Nile virus is a zoonotic infectious agent belonging to the Flavivirus family. West Nile virus has become endemic in a vast geography around the world, and is especially common in Africa, the Middle East, Asia, Europe, and North America. It is transmitted to humans through mosquito bites, and the infection can be mild in most cases. Approximately 80% of infected people do not show symptoms or only experience mild flu-like symptoms. More serious symptoms may develop in 20% of infected people, including high fever, dizziness, rashes, muscle weakness, and persistent headaches. Serious neurological complications (encephalitis, meningitis) can be seen in approximately 1% of infected people. The virus can cause more serious diseases, especially in older individuals, people with weakened immune systems, and those with certain chronic diseases. The highest risk of contracting the virus is during the summer when mosquitoes are active. Birds, in particular, are natural hosts for West Nile virus, and mosquitoes can transmit the virus to humans by contracting it from infected birds (Simonin, 2024).

West Nile virus can be diagnosed by clinical signs and serologic testing, with PCR testing confirming the presence of the virus. While there is no specific treatment, symptomatic treatment includes fluid replacement, pain and fever management, and treatment of neurological complications. Vaccines are not yet available for use in humans. Protection from the virus includes avoiding mosquito bites and taking environmental control measures. Additionally, the public and health care professionals should be educated about the symptoms of West Nile virus (Simonin, 2024).

Dengue: A systematic review by Guo et al. reveals the global distribution of dengue fever outbreaks between 1990 and 2015, highlighting that dengue fever has become prevalent in more than 100 countries worldwide, with an annual incidence of 50–100 million infections. Dengue fever is reported to pose a serious health threat (Guo et al., 2017 Guo et al., 2017).

Dengue virus is primarily transmitted by *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes, which breed in artificial water containers and bite during daylight. The virus initially infects dendritic cells before spreading to lymph nodes, liver, and spleen. Primary infections are often mild or asymptomatic, while secondary infections with a different serotype increase the risk of severe dengue due to antibody-dependent enhancement, leading to plasma leakage, shock, and organ failure. Clinically, dengue presents with sudden fever, headache, and rash in mild cases, progressing to bleeding, thrombocytopenia, and circulatory collapse in severe cases. Diagnosis relies on PCR or antigen testing early in infection, followed by IgM/IgG serology after five days. Treatment remains supportive, focusing on fluid management, as no antiviral exists. Prevention emphasizes mosquito control and cautious vaccine use, as Dengvaxia® may worsen disease in seronegative individuals (Otu, Ebenso, Etokidem, & Chukwuekezie, 2019). Dengue fever is particularly common among young adults, with children being more prone to severe forms of the disease (Martins, Prata-Barbosa, & Cunha, 2020).

Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever

Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever, an endemic zoonotic disease in Türkiye, poses a public health threat with increasing cases, especially in summer. Symptoms may include fatigue, muscle and joint pain, fever and

headache, nausea/vomiting, and diarrhea. Laboratory findings may include thrombocytopenia, elevated creatine kinase, increased aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase levels, leukopenia, elevated lactic dehydrogenase, prolonged prothrombin time, and prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time. Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever should be kept in mind in patients presenting with fever, muscle pain, headache, and thrombocytopenia, especially in the spring and summer months (Alkan-Çeviker, Günel, & Kılıç, 2019).

Rapid identification and appropriate infection control measures remain important for Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever, which does not yet have an effective vaccine and has no definitive treatment, although ribavirin is used in contact and confirmed cases. Hospitals, reference laboratories, and a one health approach that integrates public health responses are important in the outbreak response (Bartolini et al., 2019).

Measles

Due to its high transmissibility, measles requires at least 95% of the population to be vaccinated with two doses of vaccine to be eliminated. Although all WHO regions have set an elimination target, sustainable elimination has not yet been achieved. Vaccination coverage increased between 2000 and 2019; however, with the COVID-19 pandemic, it decreased to 81% in 2021. Between 2021 and 2022, the number of cases and deaths increased significantly. Measles vaccination prevented approximately 57 million deaths between 2000 and 2022 (Minta et al., 2023). Today, measles cases and measles-related deaths are increasing in many countries, especially in the United States (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2025a). Surveillance systems were also negatively affected by the pandemic. Universal implementation of vaccine, strengthening of surveillance, and rapid restructuring of immunization programs disrupted by the pandemic are required to reverse the current situation (Minta et al., 2023).

Poliomyelitis

The global incidence of poliomyelitis has been significantly reduced due to the widespread implementation of both oral and inactivated poliovirus vaccines. As of 2021, wild poliovirus type 1 remains endemic only in Pakistan and Afghanistan. Wild poliovirus types 2 and 3 have been officially declared eradicated (World Health Organization [WHO], 2025a). Family physicians working in primary health care have a critical role in continuing the polio elimination process. In this context, family physicians should monitor the administration of polio vaccines in accordance with the childhood vaccination schedule. Children who have crossed the border, migrated, or returned and whose vaccination history is uncertain must be evaluated, and completing missing polio doses for these children is essential. In addition, every suspected acute flaccid paralysis should be evaluated for possible poliovirus infection and referred to specialized health units for further examination and confirmation without delay. This practice is vital in increasing the effectiveness of the surveillance system and preventing possible outbreaks.

ONE HEALTH APPROACH TO EPIDEMIC PREPAREDNESS

The One Health approach recognizes the close interconnection of human, animal, and environmental health and proposes integrated health management in these areas (World Health Organization [WHO], 2025b). This approach plays a central role in preventing infections. In particular, vector control, strengthening animal surveillance systems, monitoring of environmental factors, increasing veterinary-human health collaborations, and the integration of public health services can reduce the spread of infectious diseases (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2023). This approach, also adopted by WONCA Europe (WONCA Europe, 2023), promotes an integrated surveillance and response system between human, animal, and environmental health. A holistic approach that includes interdisciplinary collaboration among physicians, veterinarians, and ecologists, early warning systems for the detection of zoonotic transmissions, and effective public communication strategies to reduce vaccine hesitancy and increase public participation will not only prevent the spread of infections, but also enable the construction of systems that are resilient to public health threats such as climate change, globalization, and biodiversity loss.

CONCLUSION

We are faced with increasingly complex viral threats both in our country and around the world. This comprehensive system, coupled with faster diagnostic methods and equitable vaccine distribution, holds the potential to mitigate these threats significantly. The future of research lies in developing models to predict zoonotic transmissions and building climate-resilient health systems.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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